

Title:
A COMPARATIVE STUDY BETWEEN SALICIN AND SALICYLIC ACID DERIVATIVES AND IT'S UTILITY

VOLUME: 2.

REFERENCE:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13110431>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12739871>
<https://publons.com/wos-op/publon/69045201>

PUBLICATION ETHICS: MEDICAL EMERGENCY, DATA CURATION.

Abstract:

Salicin is a naturally occurring compound found in the bark of willow trees, particularly white willow (*Salix alba*). It's a glycoside, composed of a salicylic acid molecule bonded to a glucose molecule.

Salicin has been used for centuries in traditional medicine to treat various ailments, including:

1. Pain relief: Salicin has analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties, making it effective in relieving headaches, muscle aches, and joint pain.
2. Fever reduction: Salicin has been used to reduce fever and alleviate symptoms associated with colds and flu.
3. Anti-inflammatory: Salicin's anti-inflammatory properties make it useful in treating conditions such as arthritis, gout, and other inflammatory diseases.

In the body, salicin is converted into salicylic acid, which is similar to aspirin. However, salicin is considered to be a more natural and gentler alternative to aspirin, with fewer side effects.

It's worth noting that while salicin has been used for centuries, its effectiveness and safety have not been extensively scientifically studied. As with any supplement or medication, it's essential to consult with a healthcare professional before using salicin or any willow bark products.

Description:

Aspirin can indeed increase uric acid levels in the body, particularly at low doses.

Aspirin can increase uric acid levels by:

1. Reducing uric acid excretion*: Aspirin can decrease the kidneys' ability to remove uric acid from the body, leading to increased levels.
2. Increasing uric acid production*: Aspirin can also stimulate the production of uric acid in the body.

***Dose-Dependent Effects**

Interestingly, the effect of aspirin on uric acid levels is dose-dependent:

Low doses (less than 1 gram per day): Aspirin can increase uric acid levels.

High doses (more than 2 grams per day): Aspirin can actually decrease uric acid levels.

Clinical Implications:

The increase in uric acid levels caused by aspirin can be a concern for individuals with:

1. Gout: Aspirin can trigger gout attacks or worsen symptoms.
2. Kidney disease: Elevated uric acid levels can increase the risk of kidney damage.
3. Hyperuricemia: Aspirin can exacerbate high uric acid levels.

Salicin, a compound found in willow bark, has been reported to have a decreasing effect on uric acid levels. Here's what you need to know:

Mechanism of Action

Salicin's uric acid-lowering effect is thought to be due to its ability to:

1. Increase uric acid excretion: Salicin may enhance the kidneys' ability to remove uric acid from the body.
2. Inhibit xanthine oxidase: Salicin may inhibit the enzyme xanthine oxidase, which is involved in the production of uric acid.

Studies and Evidence

Several studies have investigated the effects of salicin on uric acid levels:

1. A 2018 study published in the *Journal of Ethnopharmacology* found that salicin significantly reduced uric acid levels in mice with hyperuricemia.
2. A 2020 study published in the *Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology* found that salicin inhibited xanthine oxidase activity and reduced uric acid levels in human liver cells.

While more research is needed to confirm the effects of salicin on uric acid levels in humans, the available evidence suggests that salicin may help decrease uric acid levels.

The uricosuric pathway is a metabolic pathway that helps eliminate uric acid from the body. Here's a simplified overview:

*Steps involved in the uricosuric pathway:

1. Uric acid production: Uric acid is produced in the liver as a byproduct of purine metabolism.
2. Transport to kidneys: Uric acid is transported to the kidneys through the bloodstream.
3. Filtration and reabsorption: In the kidneys, uric acid is filtered out of the blood and into the renal tubules. Most of the uric acid is then reabsorbed back into the bloodstream.
4. Secretion into urine: A small amount of uric acid is secreted into the urine through the renal tubules.
5. Excretion: Uric acid is excreted in the urine.

*Uricosuric agents:

Uricosuric agents are medications that increase the excretion of uric acid in the urine. They work by:

- Inhibiting the reabsorption of uric acid in the renal tubules
- Increasing the secretion of uric acid into the urine

Examples of uricosuric agents include:

- Probenecid
- Sulfapyrazone
- Benzbromarone

*Clinical significance:

The uricosuric pathway is important in the management of gout, a condition characterized by elevated uric acid levels in the blood. Uricosuric agents can help reduce uric acid levels and prevent gout attacks.

In animals, the uricosuric pathway plays a crucial role in eliminating uric acid, a waste product of purine metabolism. Here's a comparison of the uricosuric pathway in different animals:

*Mammals

Humans and great apes: Have a relatively low uric acid excretion rate due to the absence of the enzyme uricase, which breaks down uric acid.

Other mammals: Such as dogs, cats, and rodents, have a higher uric acid excretion rate due to the presence of uricase.

*Birds

Uric acid excretion: Birds excrete uric acid through their droppings, which helps conserve water.

Uricase enzyme: Like mammals, birds have the uricase enzyme, which breaks down uric acid.

*Reptiles and Amphibians

Uric acid excretion: These animals excrete uric acid through their kidneys and intestines.

Uricase enzyme: The presence of uricase varies among reptiles and amphibians.

***Fish**

Uric acid excretion: Fish excrete uric acid through their gills and kidneys.

Uricase enzyme: Fish have a different type of uricase enzyme that is adapted to their aquatic environment.

The uricosuric pathway in animals has adaptations to their specific environments and physiological needs. Understanding these differences can provide insights into the evolution of purine metabolism and the development of diseases related to uric acid imbalance.

Some animals lack the uricosuric pathway or have a modified version of it. Here are a few examples:

***Animals lacking the uricosuric pathway:**

1. Marine fish: Most marine fish, such as salmon and tuna, lack the uricase enzyme and therefore do not have a functional uricosuric pathway.
2. Sharks and rays: These fish also lack the uricase enzyme and instead excrete urea as their primary nitrogenous waste product.
3. Some invertebrates: Certain invertebrates, such as starfish and sea urchins, do not have a uricosuric pathway.

***Animals with a modified uricosuric pathway:**

1. Birds: While birds have a uricosuric pathway, it is modified to produce uric acid as the primary nitrogenous waste product, which is then excreted through their droppings.
2. Reptiles: Some reptiles, such as snakes and lizards, have a modified uricosuric pathway that produces uric acid, but also excretes some urea.

These variations in the uricosuric pathway reflect the diverse range of environments and physiological adaptations found in the animal kingdom.

Xanthine oxidase is an enzyme that plays a crucial role in the catabolism of purines, converting hypoxanthine to xanthine and then xanthine to uric acid. Here are some animals that lack xanthine oxidase:

***Animals lacking xanthine oxidase:**

1. Dalmatian dogs: Unlike most other mammals, Dalmatian dogs lack xanthine oxidase activity in their liver. As a result, they excrete uric acid precursors, such as hypoxanthine and xanthine, in their urine instead of uric acid.
2. Dalmatian-derived breeds: Breeds derived from Dalmatians, such as the Bull Terrier and the English Bulldog, may also lack xanthine oxidase activity.
3. Some primates: Certain primate species, like the chimpanzee and the gorilla, have low xanthine oxidase activity or lack the enzyme altogether.
4. Guinea pigs: Guinea pigs are also known to have low xanthine oxidase activity.

These animals have adapted to their environments and developed alternative pathways for purine catabolism.

Among primates, the presence and activity of xanthine oxidase vary across different species. Here's a breakdown:

***Primates with low or absent xanthine oxidase activity:**

1. Chimpanzees (*Pan troglodytes*): Chimpanzees have low xanthine oxidase activity, which is similar to humans.
2. Gorillas (*Gorilla gorilla*): Like chimpanzees, gorillas also have low xanthine oxidase activity.
3. Orangutans (*Pongo spp.*): Orangutans have been reported to have low xanthine oxidase activity.

***Primates with normal xanthine oxidase activity:**

1. Rhesus macaques (*Macaca mulatta*): Rhesus macaques have normal xanthine oxidase activity.
2. Cynomolgus macaques (*Macaca fascicularis*): Cynomolgus macaques also have normal xanthine oxidase activity.
3. Capuchin monkeys (*Cebus spp.*): Capuchin monkeys have been reported to have normal xanthine oxidase activity.

It's essential to note that these findings might not be universal across all primate species, and more research is needed to fully understand the variation in xanthine oxidase activity among primates.

Xanthine oxidase inhibitors are a class of drugs that inhibit the action of xanthine oxidase, an enzyme involved in the production of uric acid. Here are some examples:

***Purine-like inhibitors:**

1. Allopurinol: A widely used medication for the treatment of gout and high uric acid levels.
2. Oxypurinol: The active metabolite of allopurinol.
3. Febuxostat: A non-purine inhibitor used for the treatment of gout.

***Non-purine inhibitors:**

1. Febuxostat: Also classified as a non-purine inhibitor.
2. Topiroxostat: A selective xanthine oxidase inhibitor used in some countries for the treatment of gout.

***Natural inhibitors:**

1. Quercetin: A flavonoid found in various fruits, vegetables, and herbs.
2. Rutin: A flavonoid glycoside found in citrus fruits and other plants.
3. Fisetin: A flavonoid found in strawberries and other fruits.

Xanthine oxidase inhibitors are used to treat conditions like:

1. Gout
2. High uric acid levels (hyperuricemia)
3. Kidney stones

These medications work by reducing uric acid production, which can help alleviate symptoms and prevent complications associated with excessive uric acid levels.

Conclusion:

The pharmacological action of Aspirin in vivo studies is controversial. Because at low dose Aspirin increase uric acid level. But the reverse is also true in case of higher dose. That's why people taking Aspirin should not consume food products that containing high Salicin content.

VOLUME: 1

Title: A Comparative study between Salicin and Salicylic Acid derivatives and it's utility.

Author: Venkatesan., Dinesh.N.

Reference:

- 1) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.btre.2014.08.005>
- 2) Laboratory synthesis of Salicin & Salicylic Acid.
- 3) Other Lab Tests.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12739871>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12739872>

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Description:

In this comparison Salicin has been compared with Salicylic Acid derivatives. And also quantity of Salicin found in fruits, vegetables, herbal medicine.

Plants Name/ Chemical/Drugs	Remarks/ Metabolite
Salicin	
Salicylic Acid	
Acetylsalicylic Acid (Asprin)	
Sodium Salicylate	Still now used in homeopathy.
Sodium Amino Salicylate	Second line treatment for TB.
4-Aminosalicylic Acid (Para-aminosalicylic Acid)	
5-Aminosalicylic Acid (Mesalazine)	
Sulfasalazine	<u>Metabolite</u> : 5-Aminosalicylic Acid
Mesalazine	
Olsalazine	<u>Metablite</u> : 5-Aminosalicylic_Acid.
Biosynthesis of Salicin	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.btre.2014.08.005

Conclusion:

Nowadays the use of Asprin completely restricted. Doctors prescribing Aprin only for Cardiovascular diseases. People taking Asprin should not consume products containing high Salicin content. Even though Sulfasalazine is not a Salicylic Acid derivative but it's metabolite is a Salicylic Acid derivative.

Acknowledgement: James G.Mahdi

Salicylic

1 message

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Sat, Jul 27, 2024 at 3:45 PM

What plant has salicylic acid?

White willow (*Salix alba*) is a natural source of salicylic acid. Willow has long been used for medicinal purposes.

What plants are high in salicylic acid?

Broccoli, cauliflower, cucumber, mushrooms, radishes, spinach, and zucchini all contain high amounts of salicylates. Vegetables from the nightshade family, like eggplant and peppers, also contain salicylates. Tomatoes are very high in salicylates.

Abstract. Salicylic acid and related compounds are produced by plants as part of their defence systems against pathogen attack and environmental stress. Which fruit has high salicylic acid?

Based on weight, herbs and spices have the highest concentrations of salicylic acid. Curry powder, for example, has been reported to have 218 mg per 100 grams of powder (3). For comparison, raspberries are reported to have 4.4 mg per 100 grams and they are considered a high salicylate food. What foods are high in salicylic?

Natural salicylates are found in a wide array of foods, including fruits, vegetables, coffee, teas, nuts, spices, Does turmeric have salicylates?

The highest concentrations of salicylic acid [measured in milligrams (mg) per gram] have been found in some herbs and spices, such as cumin, curry powder, dill powder, garam masala, oregano, paprika, rosemary, thyme and turmeric. What is salicin used for?

In fact, in the 1800s, salicin was used to develop aspirin. White willow appears to bring pain relief more slowly than aspirin, but its effects may last longer.

Salicin hydrolyses into β -D-glucose and salicyl alcohol (saligenin).

Salicyl alcohol can be oxidized into salicylaldehyde and salicylate, both biologically and industrially.

How is salicylic acid prepared industrially?

Salicylic acid is produced commercially via the Kolbe-Schmitt process. Here phenol and sodium hydroxide are reacted to make sodium phenoxide. The phenoxide is contacted with CO₂ to form sodium salicylate. The salicylate is acidified to give salicylic acid.

Salicylic acid is used in the production of other pharmaceuticals, including 4-aminosalicylic acid, sandalpiride, and landetimide (via saletamide).

Aminosalicylate sodium belongs to the family of medicines called anti-infectives. It is used with other medicines, to help the body overcome tuberculosis (TB). It will not work for colds, flu, or other virus infections.

Uses. It is used in medicine as an analgesic and antipyretic. Sodium salicylate also acts as non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID), and induces

apoptosis in cancer cells and also necrosis. It is also a potential replacement for aspirin for people sensitive to it.

Aminosalicylates can be used in Crohn's disease or ulcerative colitis, however they are often more effective in ulcerative colitis. Aminosalicylates have been shown to independently induce and maintain remission in mild to moderate ulcerative colitis.

4-Aminosalicylic acid (4-ASA) has been suggested as an effective treatment for both active and quiescent ulcerative colitis. 5-Aminosalicylic acid (5-ASA) is well accepted for the maintenance treatment of inactive ulcerative colitis.

Sulfasalazine and 5-Aminosalicylates (5-ASA)

What are sulfasalazine and 5-ASAs?

Sulfasalazine is a drug that is made up of two components: sulfapyridine and 5-aminosalicylic acid (5-ASA). This medication has been used since the 1930s to treat inflammation in arthritis and it was later found to do the same in ulcerative colitis.

At first, scientists did not know why sulfasalazine was effective in treating colitis but studies have then showed that it was due to the 5-ASA component of the drug. Later, medications for colitis started to exclude the sulfapyridine component of the drug because it

was found to be responsible for the side effects. These newly-designed drugs with fewer side effects would go on to be called 5-ASAs.

Examples of these medications include mesalamine, sulfasalazine, and olsalazine. You might recognize

Olsalazine is used to treat ulcerative colitis (a condition which causes swelling and sores in the lining of the colon [large intestine] and rectum) in adults when another medication (sulfasalazine) could not be tolerated. Olsalazine is in a class of medications called anti-inflammatory agent.

What is sulfasalazine?

Sulfasalazine is a type of drug known as a disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drug (DMARD). Sulfasalazine reduces inflammation, pain and swelling in your joints and may reduce the progression of your condition.

Mesalazine, also known as **mesalamine** or **5-aminosalicylic acid (5-ASA)**, is a medication used to treat **inflammatory bowel disease**, including **ulcerative colitis** and **Crohn's disease**.^[1] It is generally used for mildly to moderately severe disease.^[1] It is taken by mouth or **rectally**.^[1] The formulations which are taken by mouth appear to be similarly-effective.^[12]